

**THE GLOBAL LENS OF LEARNING: EXPLORING THE INTERCULTURAL
EXPERIENCES OF FOREIGN EXCHANGE STUDENT-TEACHERS
IN LABORATORY HIGH SCHOOL TOWARD INTER-
NATIONALIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION**

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The Global Lens of Learning: Exploring the Intercultural Experiences of Foreign Exchange Student-Teachers in Laboratory High School towards Internationalization of Higher Education

Jared Clarence Hilario,* Erica Mae T. Bagaporo, Jemimah V. Ricio, Kharylle Mhae E. Santa Ana, Mary Kathlyn R. Ticman, Angel Edie S. Villegas, Joseph A. Villarama

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Global spheres across transborder adapted to internationalizing higher education in aligning with international competencies in learning and teaching. Institutions implement student-exchange programs as step-approach opportunities in clinching global partnerships. The study phenomenologically measures the extent of international education. Internationalization as a theoretical undertaking serves as an implication of the interdisciplinarity of learning methods. With purposive sampling, a focus group semi-structured interview gathered the experiences of six (6) student-teachers from Japan, Indonesia, and Thailand. These are interdependent with the quality of international education. Responses are based on the subjects' cultural stint under Southeast Asian Teachers Exchange Program Pilot Batch 2. Data were thematically analyzed. Positive themes were observed despite the struggles. Academic freedom, and culture shock, played as some of the instrumentals and challenges, respectively. Student-teachers deem the program and internationalizing education as crucial to furthering quality education. Key findings reveal that while participants faced challenges such as culture shock and language barriers, they also experienced significant academic freedom and personal growth. The student-teachers highlighted the importance of international education in enhancing teaching competencies and fostering global awareness. The study underscores the need for sustainable internationalization efforts to ensure quality education. While internationalization resolves issues in learning, sustainability remains key as education is the backbone of any globalized arena.

Keywords: *internationalization, international education, exchange student-teachers, intercultural awareness, laboratory high school*

Introduction

Internationalization of higher education is an idealist-instrumentalist practice oriented towards presenting a globalized form of learning while advancing multiculturalism and the growth of knowledge in an international context. The end goal of internationalizing education is to raise cultural consciousness and integrate learning for transformative action (Kerkhoff & Cloud, 2020). This theoretical undertaking is a strategic approach by institutions to enrich the competitive nature of learning and ease educational tensions (Culp, 2021). At the Higher Education Thought Leaders' Conference in 2019, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) portrayed the Philippines as a supporter of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) community's identity building. Through transnational education and encouraging education research, higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines are becoming more international (Illieva & Killingley, 2015). Faculty exchange programs and extension projects are improving academic quality and amplifying international partnerships for goals (Olipas et al., 2022). Other Asian countries, including China (Wen & Wang, 2021), India (Matthews, 2021), Japan (Huang, 2021), South Korea (Choi, 2021), and Malaysia (Abdullah et al., 2021), also engage in internationalizing their respective HEIs to contribute to the interconnected global community of 21st-century education.

Philippine institutions play a crucial role in the development of internationalization. This effort has led to a rise in the demand for skilled and professional labor globally (Gao, 2020). Internationalization offers students and professors a variety of options and a fresh perspective on academia. The Philippines' relatively low cost of living compared to other Southeast Asian nations makes it a desirable place to live and work. However, the nation's approach towards international academics and student-teachers reveals some weaknesses. Despite its open attitude towards economic mobility, which has facilitated international migration, there are still challenges related to the nation's advanced education program on a global platform. Higher education institutions often prioritize low-cost, low-return programs over high-priority programs that offer greater long-term social returns (Bernardo, 2020).

The Philippine Higher Education Reform Agenda (PHERA) and various initiatives by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) aim to internationalize education through faculty exchange programs, extension projects, and international partnerships. The Department of Education has also been actively engaging in global citizenship education, aiming to enhance the educational competencies of school teachers (GovPH, 2018).

International students face both academic and cultural challenges. They must adjust to different social and academic cultures, with language barriers significantly impacting their academic performance, social interactions, and overall success. Challenges include understanding academic jargon, managing time, meeting assignment expectations, and achieving conversational fluency (Santos et al., 2022; Villarama et al., 2022). These students often struggle with course prerequisites, cooperation with peers, classroom participation, and accessing support services due to language barriers (EduBirdie, 2021).

To overcome these challenges, international students utilize campus resources such as writing centers, participate in extracurricular

activities, seek language assistance, and join student organizations. Educators play a crucial role by recognizing that native-speaker fluency is rare among international students, thus adopting more inclusive and supportive teaching methods. Providing culturally appropriate resources that account for linguistic diversity, religious beliefs, and mental health literacy is essential for the successful integration of international students (Abraham & Bromssen, 2018; Fragouli, 2020).

International students' adaptation involves overcoming culture shock and establishing relationships within their new communities. Financial issues, homesickness, and health problems are common, yet support systems within educational institutions can mitigate these difficulties, promoting a more inclusive and effective learning environment (Lai et al., 2020).

Since the National Education System Number 20's guiding principles were adopted in 2003, Indonesia has been using the system that is currently in force. The 6-3-3 structure is used consistently throughout the educational system. There are six levels for both primary and secondary education. But secondary education is divided into two, three years for junior secondary and another three years for vocational school. After twelve years of basic education, students can continue their studies by enrolling in higher education, vocational programs, and general academic programs (Sukmayadi & Yahya, 2020). Similarly, Thailand also has an education system of 6-3-3, and after that, students can enroll in higher education programs (Durongkaverroj, 2022). Moreover, Thailand's compulsory education system differs from Indonesia's in that it mandates the very first nine years of primary education.

In Japan, there are four levels of education: middle school, secondary schools, and college courses (secondary and college universities), which last a total of ten years (3-3-4). Moreover, there are private schools that offer a six-year program; combining three-year middle and three-year high school education. In addition, other specialized institutions, however, are proposing a five-year program; combining three-year high school education and two-year middle college (Elasmay Mahrous, 2021).

As for the Philippines, both formal and informal educational systems are available there. A bachelor's degree requires four years of higher education after completing four years of secondary schooling. This is referred to as the traditional education service's 6-4-4 structure. The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) supervises post-secondary and finish college academic achievement, the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) supervises technical vocational courses and middle education, and the Department of Education (DepEd) supervises pre-university education, the three agencies in charge of managing the various levels of the country's educational system (Cudy, 2022).

The Philippines began implementing the K-12 Program in 2012 as it progressed towards approaching the international standard, particularly in secondary education. As a result, fewer students enrolled in colleges. With this curriculum, the students are best prepared for lifetime learning and skills enhancement as they turn into more competent individuals (Masuhay & Herrera, 2019).

Indonesia, Thailand, and Japan have the same education system (6-3-3), while the Philippines have a different one. Despite the similar educational system among the three nations, different compulsory education systems are evident. Education is required for nine years in Thailand, nine years in Japan, twelve years in Indonesia, and thirteen years in the Philippines.

In an effort to globalize higher education in Indonesia, attitudes associated with globalization, including internationalization and multiculturalism, were advocated across all the educational institutions (Sibawaihi & Fernandes, 2022). The enhancement of national competitiveness is essential for improving internationalization (Tiyana, 2022). To help with internationalization, the general administration of higher education utilized the grade standards established by international cooperation agencies within the scope of the nation's universities and colleges. Furthermore, the state established scholarships internationally as a result of the slower growth of university education and the limitations of the teachers. They also sent instructors to pursue their doctoral and master's degrees abroad and brought in top-notch teachers from other countries to help indigenous teachers grow and develop.

Similar to other countries throughout the world, Thailand is eager to increase the scope of its foreign education program. In order to improve Thailand's educational system in the context of a multicultural population and growing cross-border mobility, the Office of Higher Education (OHEC) of Thailand presents the 15-Year Extended Range Program on Universities in Thailand (Jampaklay et al., 2022). The OHEC has approved the World Trade Organization's Joint Declaration on Trade in Services in order to advance global education. Organization for Commerce. Several of these agreements offer assistance with the construction of foreign universities' overseas branches, programs for professional exchange education, and dual degree and exchange student initiatives. The significance of bilateral cooperation among educational institutions is especially emphasized (2008-2022) in Thailand's 15-Year Long Range Plan on Higher Education, particularly in Asian nations.

It is encouraged to introduce degree programs on the international stage to strengthen the university's prestige as they contribute to the internationalization of education to have a good quality and impression when expanding the Philippine educational system toward globalization (Dotong & Laguador, 2015). As they adopt international standards and competency structures for the graduate, the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) from the majority of developed countries are offering a variety of program accreditations to support the development of strong partnerships between universities and industries in their respective regions and to engage more foreign students.

Globalization has significantly impacted university education in Japan, just like it has in other nations. Using a variety of competitive funding initiatives, the Japanese government has encouraged the internationalization of education as a prerequisite for higher education reform. Also, the significance of internationalization has grown to outweigh domestic rivalry among Japanese colleges. However, it is

uncertain whether the funding may have improved Japan's education system overall in terms of its compatibility and competitiveness with the rest of the world (Hiroshi, 2018).

In terms of intercultural competency in education, among the countries listed above, Thailand is the most competent. To be interculturally competent in education, education authorities, teachers, and students need to be interculturally competent. They must be able to communicate with those who differ from them linguistically, culturally, socially, or in other ways. The majority of Thai educators believe that teaching culture should focus on improving students' cross-cultural communication skills and raising students' knowledge of cultural differences (Fungchomchoei & Kardkarnklai, 2016). Teachers encourage students to investigate, understand, and think about the connection between language, cultural environment, and information exchange in order to increase their understanding of various cultures through the use of social media. Their way of teaching, which compares and contrasts other cultures, would also be very helpful in addressing significant barriers that prevent learners from knowing more about cross-cultural understanding (Lee et al., 2023). In light of this, students also become interculturally competent. Furthermore, with the efforts Thailand has made towards internationalization, it can be said that it is the most interculturally competent in education.

Research Objectives

The study aims to:

1. explore the intercultural competencies and pedagogical adjustments that foreign exchange student-teachers undergo while adapting to the Philippine-based educational system; and
2. analyze qualitatively the impact of the student-teacher exchange program on the personal and professional development of participating student-teachers, and its contribution to internationalizing higher education.

Methodology

Research Design

This qualitative research study employs a purposive sampling approach to select participants. The primary criterion for selection is the consent of international students, without filtering for sex, age, course undertaken, or length of experience. The study focuses on an in-depth analysis of participants' responses in relation to research objectives. It examines competencies, insights, experiences, subjective perceptions, and assessments through an intercultural lens. Culture and education serve as bases for determining the significance of these factors in the context of internationalization. The data collection and transcription are followed by a qualitative interpretation of acquired experiences and insights using a thematic analysis method to organize and code the gathered responses.

Participants

Participants are purposively selected from the SEA Teacher Exchange Program Pilot Batch 2, which includes international partnerships between Central Luzon State University (CLSU), Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia (UPI), University of Tsukuba-Japan (UT), and Khon Kaen University-Thailand (KKU). Two participants from each nationality are chosen, ensuring a diverse representation of backgrounds and experiences

Instruments

The primary research instrument used is a semi-structured interview guide. This guide includes well-planned and well-crafted questions designed to elicit detailed and meaningful responses from the participants. The interviews are recorded using video and audio recorders, with additional notes taken during the sessions to capture important information.

Procedure

Data collection involves conducting semi-structured interviews with six participants. Most interviews take place inside the Central Luzon State University campus, while online interview modality shall serve as failsafe should the interviewee is physically unavailable at the time. The researchers use video and audio recording equipment to capture the interviews, and focus group interviews are utilized to maximize the participants' stay and encourage open-ended discussions. The data collection process includes systematic searches for recurring themes in the recorded responses. Data triangulation and cross-checking are performed to secure the accuracy, reliability, and validity of the findings.

Data Analysis

Data collection involves conducting semi-structured interviews with six participants. Most interviews take place inside the Central Luzon State University campus, while online interview modality shall serve as failsafe should the interviewee is physically unavailable at the time. The researchers use video and audio recording equipment to capture the interviews, and focus group interviews are utilized to maximize the participants' stay and encourage open-ended discussions. The data collection process includes systematic searches for recurring themes in the recorded responses. Data triangulation and cross-checking are performed to secure the accuracy, reliability, and validity of the findings.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted following the guidelines of the Central Luzon State University (CLSU) Ethics Research Committee, with protocol approval code 2023-183 obtained on March 14, 2023. All participants provided informed consent, and the researchers ensured confidentiality and anonymity throughout the study.

Results and Discussion

Experiences of Student-Teachers

Student-teachers were passionate about education and wanted to teach. Their passion for teaching and their interest in education are what keep them going. The exchange student-teachers' responses' results showed their passion for teaching. The participants showed their excitement and enthusiasm in various ways. Some of them are, "I like teaching," "Students made me happy," and "I learned the language." One of the international student-teachers said, "Because I was interested in it." Furthermore, the other one said, "I wanted to study education," he also added, "To expand my perspective." According to Carbonneau, Vallerand, Fernet, and Guay (2008), passion entails emphasizing learning something new. It is continually seeking out new information and making an effort to learn. Action can be spread and sparked by passion. Passion is what drives us to seek out the novel and be open to learning. Simply said, passion is demonstrating a strong inclination and readiness by devoting time and effort to a task that one finds enjoyable or significant. Learning and experimenting with new concepts are closely tied to being passionate. Day identifies hope, loyalty, compassion, and enthusiasm as characteristics of passion that are essential to good teaching (2004). According to a study by Fabelico & Aballa (2020), "Perseverance and passion in the teaching profession influence teachers' performance." It is clearly stated in their study that the level of passion and perseverance of teachers affect their efficiency in doing their work. The passion of teachers also affects the students. The passion of teachers can be transferred to a student's work passion through emotional contagion (Gilal et al., 2022). Further, Fried (2001) describes a passionate teacher as someone who is in love with the field of knowledge, deeply excited about the ideas that change our world, and closely interested in the potentials and dilemmas of young people who come to class every day. Similarly, Zehm and Kottler (1993) define passionate teachers as those who love the work they do. Passion is essential for quality and effective learning. In addition, according to Olson (2003), when we discover our passions about teaching and learning and share them with others, the doors are open, and everything becomes possible.

In the Student Teacher Exchange Program, the teachers toured the CLSU campus. Upon arriving at USHS, one of the respondents described it as "chaotic but positive." Both the students and the teachers were excited to meet each other. The students were very enthusiastic towards the foreign student-teachers and they felt flattered. They noticed similarities between the facilities in Indonesia and the Philippines which made them feel at home. "When taking a tour of CLSU, it feels like home." Further, the Student-Teacher Exchange Program includes touring and exploring several cultures of the visited country in different ways. The respondents' visited various destinations in CLSU and the Philippines. They have noticed comparisons between the two countries. They got immersed in the new culture but they still hold on to their own culture which is why they can come to compare them. When being immersed in another culture, one experiences feelings of being open to new cultural experiences; yet one holds on to one's own national culture through comparisons while at work and in non-work situations (Russell, 2009). Gabel, Dolen and Cerdin (2005) defined cultural adjustment as the changes that individuals undergo to form a relationship with the host society. According to Constantine, Okazaki and Utsey (2004), cultural adjustment involves the process of understanding and incorporating behaviors, values and beliefs of the host culture in the perspective of the one's own culture of origin. Kagan and Cohen, (1990) have defined cultural adjustment in terms of a process that involves several interrelated factors associated with behavioral, cognitive, affective and demographic aspects and that results in different levels of adjustment from cultural assimilation to cultural transmutation.

There were different processes in the selection of teachers in the student-teacher Exchange program. These include promoting and volunteering. In the case of one of the student-teachers, he was called by someone who shared or promoted the program with him. While in the case of one of the respondents, she volunteered to join while no one else did. This was also the student-teachers' first time teaching. There were also complications in joining the program according to one of the students-teachers' participants, where otherwise, her friends would have joined as well. They joined the program because they see it as an opportunity to discover and experience something new. "I want to teach, especially in another country, so it would be interesting." In the Fulbright Teacher Exchange Program, the application processes and instructions include an online application, paper application, signing of the terms and agreements, deadline, references, related documentation, all future communication, specific address, application checklist page, interview sites, format, modern foreign language proficiency, present employment, daily schedule for the current year, and accommodations are among the various requirements for the application for the program (Fulbright Teacher Exchange Program, 2008).

Importance of the Student-Teacher Exchange Program

The student-teacher Exchange Program enables student-teachers to become fully immersed in a different academic environment. It has given student-teachers the chance to encounter a totally different culture. Also, experiential learning abroad improves your communication abilities. A student-teacher stated, "I learned to cope with different cultures and I realized things that should be improved in the education system of my country." Moreover, the student-teacher argued that the teacher-centered model should be replaced with a student-centered one in their nation because students in the latter appear to be more involved and critical of their

learning. “Compared to this, USHS, it’s always fun to teach at USHS. Because here you will accept the way they support you and when they will solve problems maybe in an unusual way, maybe in some clear way...” Another student-teacher stated, “I feel appreciated when you help the students to solve their problems, and help them achieve what they want to achieve. So, I think it’s really helpful to use a student-centered approach in schools.” According to Viktoriia, (2022), having a varied perspective on the world helps you understand your place in the global community. A crucial advancement of the student-teacher curriculum is the transformation of teacher development through an exchange program as an empowering tool (Lydia & Coetzer et al., 2017). Wendy Li (n.d.) asserts that experiencing a different culture and educational system while studying abroad increases one’s desire to learn and use newfound talents. Instead of portraying the instructor as the subject matter expert in charge of transferring knowledge to his or her pupils through lectures and direct teaching, teachers and students should work together as partners in the learning process, with the student playing a more active role in their education. (Catherine, 2021)

Being culturally aware is crucial for educators because it enables them to relate to and comprehend people from all backgrounds. When asked about their preparation before going to the Philippines, one of the respondents replied, “The one thing I remember is that I just searched, ‘How do I teach?’, you know academic stuff, only that one.” Another said, “So that’s basically how I prepare myself, doing some research.” Adding to his previous statement, “I researched– like ‘The food here is this and that’ and ‘How do you speak here?’ I’m really glad that you guys can speak English and treat English as your second language because that’s the only international language that I can do.” One must take advantage of this chance to experiment with various teaching techniques and determine which style of instruction best suits them. Cultural material is viewed as crucial as a way to teach in order to improve language proficiency, cultural comprehension, and appreciation of diversity (B.W. Haas, 2018; Rasulov, 2002). However, teaching a language is not only about teaching the language itself (Valdes, 1986). As Brookfield (1995) has observed, in order to understand teaching, teachers have to make sense of their own knowledge and beliefs and how these influence their practice. In addition, Mckay (1993) points out that multicultural classrooms exist throughout the world. In a multicultural classroom, in which teachers and students originate from different backgrounds, both students and teachers may approach the situation with different cultural values and expectations about their roles (Mckay, 1993). Therefore, culture is a significant component in second and foreign language education.

Studying abroad gives you the chance to learn about your host nation’s history, culture, cuisine, and language. You can have a fresh appreciation for your own culture as a result. A fresh perspective on the world helps you understand your place in the larger community of humanity. Student-teachers from Indonesia believe that aside from the expensiveness of the program, the student-teacher Exchange Program has a lot of benefits and potential. The participant said, “This is an expensive program but I think the experience you’ll gain is what is expensive. I recommend that others grab this once-in-a-lifetime opportunity.” The Indonesians also put into detail what they have learned based on their experiences while teaching at CLSU Science High School. These include, “How to behave, how to be initiative–how to manage proactively, and etiquette stuff. I also learned about proper engagement with high school students, delivery of material, and how to make time management easy,” and “...here I learned there are a lot of ways to make the student more engaged in learning, like in English, and watching educational stuff.” Additionally, “How do we make the class fun and improve students’ oral thinking skills, I learned about classroom management, you can’t always be polite, you should be strict sometimes.” Employers can notice your diversity through your study abroad experience, as well as your willingness to take on new challenges and push yourself outside of your comfort zone. (Sisavath, 2021).

The Thai student-teachers believed in the importance of education. Additionally, they thought that exchange programs are a great help in developing personal growth, especially in improving their knowledge of the language of other countries. “I believe that education is important because it is the foundation of everything, additionally, I think that it is extremely helpful and effective (exchange programs). It gives the students the opportunities and experiences abroad, and I hope that more Thai people can learn to speak in English because it can help them to communicate more in other countries.” Education is a lifelong process (Blossfeld & Maurice, 2019). It helps people gain knowledge, which can be used to improve skills needed later in life. One way of gaining knowledge is through exchange programs. International Teacher Exchange programs give teachers opportunities to learn more about other cultures, teaching methods, curricula, and rules and laws about educational programs in other educational environments (Milian, 2022). With an increasing awareness of various cultures, current events, and resources used by other countries for successful teaching, exchange programs can greatly benefit student instructors. (Marco & Kreis et al., 2022).

Education System in Global Spheres

Based on the student-teacher’s response, the educational system in Japan is quite authoritative compared to the educational system in the Philippines. Because the curriculum is overpowering, and the amount of content is maximized. As stated by one of the international student-teachers, “It’s like kind of strict in rules of what to teach.” Moreover, the other international student-teacher told that “Also, the level of content of the Math classes is high, especially in CLSU Science High School.” There are several advantages to autonomy-supportive education for both students and teachers. In other words, students typically become more motivated and engaged when teachers support their initiative and take into account their point of view (Tsai et al., 2008), while teachers see an increase in teaching effectiveness and work satisfaction (Cheon et al., 2014). Support for autonomy by itself has a lot of advantages. Yet, a teacher’s structure may or may not improve students’ motivation, engagement, and performance on its own (Grolnick & Pomerantz, 2009). According to a gradually increasing number of studies, controlling structures undermine motivation and produce few positive effects, while autonomous structures foster motivation and produce a wide range of positive effects (Carpentier & Mageau, 2013, 2016; Cheon

et al., 2019, Curran et al., 2013, Eckes et al., 2018, Koestner et al., 1984, Mouratidis et al., 2010, Mouratidis et al., 2018, Ryan, 1982, Trouilloud et al., 2006, Vansteenkiste et al., 2012).

The education systems in the Philippines and Japan are revealed to be representations of up-to-date learning and education as determined by the international student-teachers. "Education in Japan...even if you are very clever and smart, you have to study with people the same age as you are. Sometimes, it is good, but sometimes, bad," the international student-teacher said. In addition, "But, academic freedom, that is what I get excited about the most and find it interesting and fascinating," stated the other international student-teacher. Thus, according to Anthony (1996), active learning builds on prior information, involves knowledge building as opposed to knowledge absorption, and is conscious of the learner. Similarly, to this, Prince (2004) believes that active learning occurs when students participate actively in the learning process and critically evaluate the information they are given, as opposed to merely copying and regurgitating academic stock.

Education system in Indonesia faced various problems especially when the COVID-19 pandemic happened. These include recovering from the pandemic, changes in the curriculum, unreadiness of teachers to teach, lack of interest of students, inefficient work ethic and discipline, stiff atmosphere in class, lack of control in managing the class, and no academic freedom (Villarama et al., 2022). Comparing these to the education system in the Philippines, the student-teachers believe that the Philippines has better approaches regarding education. "I think it's really helpful to use a student-centered approach in schools," one of the student-teachers stated. As the teachers in Indonesia encountered difficulties in teaching especially in the time of pandemic due to limitations in accessing the internet, difficulties in explaining the lessons, student's economically disadvantaged background and parents' support system (Lestiyawati, 2020). Because of the propensity to call rote learning, learning components are short in supply in Indonesia. Furthermore, having a high cost of learning materials such as textbooks, school items, teaching materials, and teacher training programs results in poor quality of education (Shaturaev, 2021).

Thailand and the Philippines have both differences and similarities in terms of education systems. The student-teachers have shared that the way of teaching of both Thai and Filipino teachers has no difference but the way the students are participating is different. The student-teachers stated "the students in Thailand are so shy, but in the Philippines, the students are more active (always talking, sharing their thoughts and ideas) and smiling," and "Teachers in Thailand and Philippines are very similar when they teach." It shows that social behaviors of the students and teachers have an impact on the cultural differences of each country. According to Buasuwan (2018), in order for Thailand to be competent internationally, it is important to nourish creativity, inclusionary, and sustainability to be more aware of others' culture and learn more about private and public community engagement.

Experiences in the Academe and Cultural Context

The Japanese international student-teachers acknowledged that the students expressed hail-fellow-well-met interactions. They noticed the setting as well as the children's incredibly good-natured and positive attitudes. As stated by the international student-teacher, "Smart people tend to be exclusive like 'I don't talk to you'," like that. But they are not like that. They are accepting and they listen to my English so that we can get a mutual understanding," and "Just listen to reality, listen to what people say, and compare yourself but don't judge." From the other international student-teacher, "Thankfully, my cooperating teacher gave me lots of advice, so I was able to apply my lessons." Strong relationships between students and teachers serve as a stabilizing foundation for long-term student learning (Hamre & Pianta, 2001). Students typically perform better in school and are more engaged when they know their teachers appreciate them (Wang & Eccles, 2013). Many studies have revealed that students with close teacher ties are more likely than those with more distant relationships to have academic interest, engagement, success, self-efficacy, and motivation (Fast et al., 2010; Sakiz, Pape, & Hoy, 2012; Tosto, Asbury, Mazzocco, Petrill, & Kovas, 2016; Wentzel, Battle, Russell, & Looney, 2010).

The international student-teachers widely recognized that they personally encountered exhaustion and faced challenges. "Learning something new and something not relevant to myself like that is not something I've been used to. It was actually tiring." "It was a big challenge for me to teach there because it was my first-time teaching in class." While adjusting to life in the host country, international student-teachers may encounter cultural shock in addition to other difficulties like being away from their family and a lack of social support (Arasaratnam and Doerfel, 2005; Hendrickson et al., 2011; Smith and Khwaja, 2011; Spencer-Rogers and McGovern, 2002; Williams and Johnson, 2011). It may be more challenging for the student-teachers to make correct predictions and interpretations of the actions in the host culture the farther the native culture is from the host culture (Furnham and Bochner, 1982; Redmond and Bunyi, 1993). Additionally, as student-teachers grow personally, develop as independent thinkers, and become agents of change, their perspectives are challenged (Lillyman and Bennett, 2014).

The similarities in Indonesia and in the Philippines in terms of academics that the teachers noticed are that teachers are underpaid, they have packed schedules and K-12 education. "I think for me, the similarities that I can see are: Teachers being underpaid, the whole day schedule, 12 years of education, and like the full-time schedule." Fifty percent of Filipinos think public school teachers 'are underpaid' (Gatchalian, 2022; Villarama et al., 2023). Based on my conversations with teachers and school leaders in various countries, teacher salaries are often at the top of the list. Teachers argue that they need higher salaries so as not to need to spend their time racing around to side jobs in order to be able to support their families. They also argue that high pay will increase professionalism or induce higher effort through a sense of reciprocity. The Government of Indonesia opted to double the base pay of civil service teachers, which translated to a two-thirds increase in net pay for teachers eligible for the reform. As a result, teachers earned more, were happier, faced

less financial stress, and fewer held second jobs (Evans, 2018). We can relate these to the statement “Teachers being underpaid” by the respondent.

The student-teachers from Thailand had made fostering relationships and positive reinforcements from teaching experience with the students and their co-teachers as they are inside and even outside a learning environment. They have also come to reach their expectations in teaching when they were in the Philippines with the statement “I think students here make me know or learn everything and make me very happy and make me enjoy my stay here.” Based on the study of Astrid (2019), initiating connectivity in a community is important before engaging into an organization where there is no connection between the people. It proves that building a good relationship will help more with the interactions between the students and the teachers inside a classroom.

Struggles, Adaptations, and Personal Development

Language has been a problem for foreign teachers whenever they are in other countries. Whether they are teaching or not, the difference between the language they are used to and the language they use to teach (foreign language), makes it difficult for them to communicate. Some of the Thai teachers said, “It is hard to speak in English because in Thailand we don’t speak English, we speak in Thai every time.” “We only learn English for one hour a week.” According to a study by Ulla (2018), teaching the English language in Thailand is quite challenging. Because of the unclear and unsuitable curriculum, lack of exposure and support, and lack of professional teacher development, Thailanders were unable to learn and speak the English language efficiently.

Additionally, technology in the Philippines is not advanced, which is why international student-teachers have difficulty teaching. Some of the teachers stated that “The internet is so slow.” “In Thailand, we have 5G.” “I think it was the problem for me because sometimes we need it to teach students, and we also have to search for information.” According to the study of Raja and Nagasubramani (2018), technology has revolutionized the field of education. With access to the Internet, teachers can play educational videos for students and search for necessary information for lessons. But the lack of internet access and its speed has made it difficult for teachers to teach. As stated in the study of Azcaraga and Peña (2019), the internet quality in the Philippines is quite problematic. According to the final report of the 2022 Digital Quality of Life (DQL) Index conducted by cybersecurity company Surfshark, the Philippines ranked 45th in terms of internet availability among 117 countries. Compared to Thailand, the Philippines’ internet quality is comparatively mediocre.

The student-teachers from Thailand have acquired cultural insights into the Philippines during their stay here. The student-teachers gained and acquired cultural insights and experiences during their stay in the Philippines. Some of them are “When I came here, I learned about the language, the technology, the culture, the foods.” “We also started to walk when going to school.” “I love it, it is fun, new to us, and good for you.” The cultural differences have enabled the student-teachers to acquire new abilities to function well in an unfamiliar cultural setting (Ward and Szabó, 2019).

The two Indonesian student-teacher participants, who are both majoring in English Language and are currently in their third year of study, acknowledged that they lack teaching experience in their home country. Teachers confront difficulties both within and outside of the classroom, according to Hegwood (2019), some of these difficulties include getting student teachers to adapt to a new or unusual learning style and coming up with exciting lesson plans that meet the curriculum, both of which can be overwhelming.

Religious issues are frequently complicated by cultural differences (Williams, 2006). In Indonesia, the majority of people practice Islam (Sodiman, & Abdurahman, et al., 2022). As a result, food has been a concern for the student-teachers in Indonesia; there is a huge global food market. It may be called a way of life. Because the Philippines is recognized for its great meat production, according to Statista (2022), it allows individuals to experience their background, culture, traditions, and emotions (EduBirdie, 2021). “You include pork in everything. Like a staple. This makes it extremely difficult for us to avoid temptations.” However, thanks to the support they gained throughout the program, the student instructors were able to get over the differences in culture.

Approaching the Internationalization of Higher Education

The student-teachers from Thailand believe that engaging with programs like student-teacher exchange programs would have a good contribution in approaching the internationalization of higher education. As it would boost cross-cultural exchange between countries. “I believe that students in Thailand should participate more in activities like this.” “They learn about the differences in information and cultures, I think that’s good,” said by both the student-teachers. Participating with programs as such would help the people in other countries to know and to understand the cultures and the education system in other countries that can be a big contribution in internationalizing higher education. As the student-teachers who are participating in this program are being exposed to international themes in which they are developing their education departments in order to achieve being competent to work internationally (Abraham & Bromssen, 2018). There are some factors that are needed in order to achieve the internationalization of higher education. These include the preparations of student-teachers to have experience and feedback with their fellow students, teachers, and others to be able to work on different education systems and practices that would expand our knowledge to contribute in internationalizing higher education (Fragouli, 2020).

Conclusions

International exchange programs presented both challenges and opportunities. In the case of foreign student-teachers, challenges

regarding the differences in educational set-up, environment, and culture arose. Language barriers and technological differences made it much harder for the student-teachers. They had problems with communicating and teaching because of the gaps in language and technology. Nevertheless, the knowledge and experiences they gained during their stay improved not only their educational competence but also their cultural and social awareness. International student-teachers felt included because of the supportive and cooperative environment they were in. With the supervision of the teachers and the cooperation of the students, international student-teachers learned a lot regarding teaching styles and other methods of teaching.

In general, all the experiences of the student-teachers, whether inside or outside of teaching and learning, helped to prove the point of internationalization. Thus, internationalization needs to take place as it not only enhances global competency but also expands the opportunities for everyone to explore. This is the reason why this study explores the experiences of international student-teachers, to emphasize the importance of internationalizing higher education. Furthermore, this study would help people in the fields of educational and cultural research through the study's goals of delegating high-quality education and bolstering efforts of higher education institutions to internationalize the educational system.

The researchers recommend conducting a case study instead of phenomenological study. It is also recommended to change the setting of the research to classroom so the researchers can see the actual experiences of the participants on hand. The researchers also aim to explore more about the culture and education systems of other ASEAN countries. Moreover, it is advised to conduct research at an institutional level before conducting international research. It could help the researchers to further understand the education system in other countries if they know how the education system works within their own country. Also, the researchers recommend increasing the sample size to amplify the data for the results and discussion. Furthermore, it is suggested to improve the methodology and structure of the interview to exhaust enough data from the responses of the participants.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jared Clarence Hilario

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Erica Mae T. Bagaporo

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Jemimah V. Ricio

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Kharylle Mhae E. Santa Ana

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Mary Kathlyn R. Ticman

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Angel Edie S. Villegas

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Joseph A. Villarama

Central Luzon State University – Philippines